

Concepts and senses in visual art: Through the example of analysis of some works by Bruegel the Elder

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Abstract

The conceptuality of works of visual art is a manifestation of the conceptuality of sign systems in general. In visual art, concepts rely upon verbal sign systems, including texts that prevail in culture, as well as upon sign systems of visual art and its most famous works. Conceptual schemes are intensified by metaphors, metonymies, and interrelations of denotations and connotations. Basic senses of the entire conceptual scheme and separate concepts are accompanied by various meanings of visual signs. Developed manifestations of such conceptuality are revealed in the course of analysis of Pieter Bruegel the Elder's works, in which some Hieronymus Bosch's concepts and visual signs are used.

Keywords: semiotics; sign system; concept; sense; Pieter Bruegel the Elder; Hieronymus Bosch.

1. Introduction

Interrelations of conceptual schemes, separate concepts, conceptualization, and meaning are important objects of semiotic research. Works of visual art are a peculiar area where these semiotic universals are manifested. In this field, conceptuality is indissolubly connected with the modeling, forming, and functioning of sign models of reality in communication. Models of reality that lay the foundation for many artworks possess the character of developed conceptual schemes, which might be connected with the views of semiotics in complex models (Sebeok 1999; Danesi 1999). Concepts link the systems of signs proper and denotations. Here, visual sign systems of icons, indexes, and symbols are connected with verbal sign systems. Concepts correlate structures of sign systems to the structures of other sign systems and reality. This correlation is actualized as meaning. Otherwise stated, conceptualization is the basis of

sense (Quine 1973; Laurence and Margolis 1999). Separate concepts in a work are formed according to a general conceptual scheme. Therefore, the general sense of a conceptual scheme (model) is differentiated into several senses. Verbal systems promote formation of conceptual models to a great extent. Visual sign systems refer to reality not only via icons and indexes, but also via symbols, and through symbols — via verbal systems. On the whole, concepts of visual sign systems in artworks rely upon verbal and visual sign systems that were created earlier in visual art (typical combinations of objects and signs that function in visual culture and separate works, typical cultural texts, are used). In visual sign formations of artworks, concepts can form hypertexts. The models, based on conceptualization of perceptions of the works, appear as some complicated ideas. Such works are of a verbal character. They are easily described in words. In cognition, the works that contain developed conceptual models function as a scientific concept or theory. By perceiving the environment, people produce visual information on the basis of conceptual schemes. Concepts of verbal origin participate in this information production by a person. Any fragment of visual information can be interpreted on the basis of conceptualization, and it gains sense due to this. Under certain organization of sign formations, houses, bits of furniture, clothes, and interrelations of these objects in a depicted situation become elements of conceptual schemes.

Concepts are the tools of scientific cognition. As far as art is concerned, their role is more essential in communication — in achieving clarity and integrity of the models that the communicators exchange. Therefore, in art, conceptuality is developed in the periods of integration and polarization of views (during formation of social movements, moral-religious theories, polarization of political forces, political discourses, etc). Verbal concepts of social character are transformed into visual sign systems and, vice versa, concepts that are formed in visual sign systems are verbalized, apprehended. In scientific cognition, concepts form the picture of the investigated fragments of reality, conceptions, and theories. In visual art, conceptual models design the picture of the life of society and a person, highlighting discrepancies, contradictions, demonstrating the absurdity of the events that are taking place, and revealing the solutions to vital problems. They are central elements of communication. The communicative function of concepts in visual art is actualized due to relations of concepts with nonverbal elements of the works. Concepts are developed in metaphors, metonymies, systems of denotations and connotations, they are expressed by sign formations of organizing character. Conceptualization in art is most naturally rendered in allegories. Allegory is a concrete metonymy and “aims” to turn into a concept. From this point of view, the artworks of Northern Europe in the Reformation period are of crucial importance for study of concepts and conceptualization. Allegories of Hieronymus Bosch, Lucas Cranach the Elder, Hans Holbein the Younger, Hans Baldung Grien, Albrecht Dürer, and other

greatest masters of the period were the basis of conceptualization. These tendencies were developed in the works by Pieter Bruegel the Elder. Social-political contexts fostered the conceptualizations of his art. Transition to secular capitalistic society was accompanied by confrontation of secular state and the church, re-distribution of property in favor of the growing layer of capitalists and secular power. Generally speaking, the struggle between various social groups was escalating. Visual art became part of social communications, an arms for social groups to fight (Bosing 1973). Biblical verbal texts and visual images of the surrounding world were combined in the art of this period with the concepts of social-political context. In particular, H. Bosch's works played an important role in the denunciation of the church (Bosing 1973). For these reasons, Bruegel's works continued some Bosch's allegories and concepts. Further, in the course of analysis of two of Bruegel the Elder's works, I will try to demonstrate the way concepts are formed in interrelations with basic metonymies, denotations, connotations, and sign forms of the works of visual art.

2. Concepts and signs of *The land of Cockaigne*

The land of Cockaigne (1567; figure 1) met the saying "There is nothing more stupid than being lazy and greedy for sweets" and the poem by Hans Sachs with an imaginary land of idlers. As researchers noted, in this picture of pre-revolutionary years, idleness and laziness, inactivity and inertness of the society that gives itself over to dreams of well-being, are blamed. Correspondingly, typical social classes are depicted in this painting: a knight (soldier), a peasant, and a schoolboy. A famous land, described in fairy-tales, is also reflected in it. To get into the land of Cockaigne, one should have eaten a gate in the mountain of porridge. As researchers believe, this gate is depicted in the right upper corner of the painting; here, there are also a wicker fence of sausages, a hut roof covered with pies, and a number of other delicacies. At the doorstep of the hut a man is lying with open mouth who is waiting for a fried pigeon to fly into his mouth. These famous denotations of the painting form a visual denotation connected with cultural texts.

Bosch's signs and sign systems of Bruegel's *The land of Cockaigne* are similar. Circles of delicacies in the circles of dishes — H. Bosch's sign of gluttony. This system is most developed in the *Allegory of gluttony and lust* (figure 2).

Sign systems of the conceptual scheme of the painting, various metaphors, metonymies, and connotations conditioned by this scheme are less obvious. *The metonymy of a different reality* lies in the basis of the discrepancy. The conceptual reality does not correspond to a plausible one. This creates the basis for irony and sarcasm.

The land of Cockaigne by Bruegel also continues *The ship of fools* by Bosch (figure 3). A space of a different world where its own laws operate is created. This is a space inhibited by specific characters and filled with specific objects. Some signs foster formation of phantasmagoria. In the works of fantastic and surrealist character there must exist signs that point at the unreality of the depicted, at the fact that everything happens in a different, strange reality. The main sign system that is of a queer character is that in the center of the painting, a construction of a table with dishes through which a tree is growing. As will be demonstrated later, this sign system is, first of all, important to indicate the unreality of the depicted situation. Semantic relations of a different situation are produced by Saul Aaron Kripke. The mast of the tree-ship that grows through the ship or a house is a favorite of Bosch's phantasmagoria. This "strange tree" varies in his paintings many times (figures 4 and 5). Bosch's "strange tree" combines various concepts: Noah's Ark, the ship that saves sinners' souls, the mast of the ship of stupid monks who wallowed in sins of gluttony and lust (Bosing 1973). In *The land of Cockaigne*, the "strange tree" synthesizes the features of this formation from Bosch's various paintings. In addition, it symbolizes the wheel of fortune in the painting. The egg walking on its feet also acts as a sign of unreality. Its unreality is a sign of unreality of the whole depicted picture (figure 6). This allows perceiving the oddities of what is happening without contradictions with knowledge. The oddities are inconsistencies of a semantic character that form the nature of laughter, according to traditional views (Bergson 1940). Here, semantic inconsistencies arise. They are connected with the basic conceptual scheme of the work and promote the intensification of the meaning of absurdity.

Unreality of the fragment depicted in the painting points at the fact that *The land of Cockaigne* is an imagined reality. At the same time, the plausibility of the characters and objects forms its link with the reality of the setting. If it is a model of society, the depicted objects and their relations are components of the sign model of the land, i.e., their link to the land is established. At the same time, their absurdity introduces a general meaning of absurdity into this model of the land. The model of the society relies upon several interrelated metonymies. These are the metonymies of idleness, gluttony, and swinishness. They are formed on the basis of the allegories, verbal texts, and connotations that were created previously.

The metonymy of idleness is based upon denotations — portrayals of the main characters, connotations — compositions that accompany the sprawled figures. The denotations of this metonymy are the main characters of the painting, which represent social groups: a military man, a merchant, a peasant, and a woman who is baking pancakes. The characters are in a sleepy, calm state. Their figures seem to be scattered. The sleeping people are in free, natural poses.

The denotations, continued in connotations, form a substantial area of signs. The idlers that lay sprawled in twisted poses have peculiar structural formations (figures 7–11). Zigzag twists indicate laziness. The scattered figures and objects accompany carelessness and slovenliness. Heavy sleep combined with the unsteadiness of earth creates the meaning of dangerous carelessness.

As the author strove to show previously, sign systems based on geometrical elements in space — correlations of surfaces, axes, relations of the ways of motion, tilting of lines — are essential semantic elements of Bruegel's works (Somov 2009). In the painting in question, the geometrical peculiarities of the three-dimensional (the depicted) space are representaments of a single sign system that forms the meanings of carelessness, stagger, disorder, instability, disruption, twist. The meaning that is close to disruption is formed by geometrical bodies. Geometry of the bodies that fly apart to spirals and circles is also created.

The absurdity of *The land of Cockaigne* is thus supplemented by a number of connotations that develop this meaning. Such meanings accompany connotations of crookedness. The depicted earth surface is a dynamic slope that goes right down. The ground in the painting seems to tilt. This creates the state of insecurity of the foundation on which the land of the idlers reposes. This meaning is intensified by dynamic configurations and forms of the objects. A lopsided tree is rising from the ground. A circle of the table with plates and dishes is crookedly pulled on it. The earth's circles and spirals that slide down and whirl, circular movements of the dishes and lying people produce the impression of a single gyre. This gyre is intensified by s-shaped motions of the soldier's figure and the fried chicken in the plate. Circular movements of the earth and the disk with the dishes are made in different surfaces. This ever more intensifies the meaning of uncertainty and lopsidedness, and creates the feeling of gyre of various surfaces. The crookedness of surfaces with circles is strengthened by an abrupt tilt of the surface of the roof with bread on the left, the non-horizontal position of the plate with the fried goose, and the dynamics of the walking egg. The lines of the seashores that are sliding down and the oblique line of the sea horizontal also contribute to the general dynamics and obliqueness. On the whole, the meaning of unsteadiness of the earth, as if it were tilting on the waves, is created.

The metonymy of gluttony continues that of idleness, as idleness is accompanied by pleasant feelings of gluttony. Separate objects connect the basic semantics: the meanings of laziness, gluttony, and swinishness. The total construction of semantics in the work is represented by developed sign systems. In the periods of the Middle Ages and the Renaissance, gluttony became a peculiar subject of comedic culture, which was reviewed in the course of analysis of François Rabelais's poetics (Bakhtin 1993 [1965]). It was continued in the European literature in order to create a number of images. The themes of hams,

fowl legs, and fat fish acquired the character of considerable generalizations in satirical masterpieces, and promoted the formation of the metonymies of spiritless existence and pleasures of life, complacency, and inanity of living. These signs turned into global metonymies in literature. Sign systems of the *Land of Cockaigne* also fit in this general European tradition. Gluttony signs are thoroughly developed in the painting.

To develop sign systems of this theme, P. Bruegel had not only the verbal basis but visual sign systems of his predecessors as well. First of all, these were the H. Bosch's works. The metonymy of *The land of Cockaigne* continues the *Allegory of gluttony and lust* by Bosch (Figure 2). This continuation is manifested in the repetition of the basic colors: pinkish, yellow, ochreous, and dark-greenish. This color spectrum in which yellow and pinkish-brownish colors mark gluttony and lust is developed in *The land of Cockaigne* by Bruegel as well.

Fat carcasses, hams, and pigs depicted in the painting mark the pleasures of spiritless living. The objects of animal needs happen to be in the center of dreams and accompany the pleasant feelings of being asleep. The sleeping idlers feel a well-settled world around them, in which tidbits are served. For these reasons, denotations and connotations of the fried carcasses are essential signs. In the painting *Allegory of gluttony and lust*, Bosch depicted a meat pie on a plate, which a glutton who is swimming in water carries on his head. Light circles with brownish fillings of food are signs of gluttony in the painting. Following these signs, P. Bruegel developed the repetition of circles with carcasses in the centers into an organizing sign system of *The land of Cockaigne*. H. Bosch's sign systems also see other continuations in P. Bruegel's painting that are connected with gluttony. In particular, the walking egg of *The land of Cockaigne* is a modification of the walking egg of *The last judgment* by Bosch (central panel of the triptych, 1500s, Akademie der bildenden Künste, Vienna, Austria). In *The last judgment*, the egg was depicted with a hatching germ pierced by an arrow. It was subjected to an attack of an enemy. In the general context of the dreadful vision, this egg is perceived with fear. In contrast with Bosch's egg, the egg of *The land of Cockaigne* is neatly eaten away with a spoon, calmly, quietly, and heartily. This looks funny. Bruegel used Bosch's phantasmagoria to express a new meaning: walking eggs go to the gluttons themselves to be eaten and carry neat spoons with them.

Other signs of gluttony are rendered by round frying pans. They are brightly marked by color. Round configurations transform these signs into connotative formations. The pans materialize the more general circular constructions of the painting. These circles are similar to the circles of the plates, dishes, pans. The composition in general submits to circular configurations. The fried food marks the land of idlers, which becomes the food for other gluttons, the idlers will

become their victims. The twisted poses of the figures, similar to carcasses, promote this meaning. The composition in general also corresponds to it, reminding one of a big pan with appetizing meal.

The signs of rounded hams, idlers that are closed, twisted, enjoying satiety and sleep are expressed by denotative, connotative, and organizing sign forms. These sign forms of the work are organized by single structures. The turns of flat circles along their axes are created (figures 6 and 7). People are similar to carcasses and hams. The analogy of the figures lying around, fried carcasses on round pans and the egg that is eaten out produce the metaphor of the eaten, being eaten, fried dish. This contributes to the general metonymy of the land of the idlers. The country sleeps on a big dining table or a big frying pan and therefore is designed to be eaten. These signs are actualized in a common geometrical form. In this context, the configuration in which small elements are placed into a circle acquire the character of a semantic system (figure 7). The main circle that is on a tree contains the circles of the pans with the dishes, first of all these are the fried carcasses. Figures of sleeping idlers are included into the circle of the earth. This similarity creates another one in the semantic system: the circles include present and future carcasses. The walking egg half-eaten by an unknown glutton fosters the actualization of this meaning. This idea was expressed in the twentieth century by Rene Magritte, who depicted a frying pan with an egg being fried, from which a human eye stares directly at a spectator. This surrealistic image combines an egg-victim from *The land of Cockaigne* by Bruegel and the eyes of God-tabletop by Bosch. Numerous circles also indicate bread and pancakes. The roof is covered with them. According to a Flandrian saying, these are “pancakes on a roof,” which was earlier depicted by Bruegel in *Netherlandish proverbs*.

Denotations and connotations of swinishness complement the meanings of idleness and gluttony. In the culture of this period, a pig was a sign of everything rough and spiritless, the simplest and the most understandable sign of obscene life. Bosch depicted swine as symbolization of vices. “Do not cast roses before the swine” is one of folk sayings of Flanders that Bruegel illustrated in the painting *Netherlandish proverbs*. Therefore, the depiction of swine was the most effective sign to introduce the features of overall swinishness into the painted land. To concretize this meaning, a small pig is shown behind a hillock on the background. This small denotation turns into a great connotation. Expanding in color configurations and contours, a small swine with a knife in its side grows up into great swinishness (figure 12). The features of the bristling wool introduce vitality, dynamics, and plausibility into this connotation. The wool is materialized in the contours of a big swine by fences and trees of the landscape. The whole bending earth of the land of idlers becomes similar to a back of a big bristling swine. This connotation is formed by the features of the outlines.

A strange tree is the center of composition, as was noted earlier. The significance of this object also presupposes its semantic role in the sign system. The origin of the meaning is based upon the general conceptualization. The conceptual scheme of the strange tree of *The land of Cockaigne* requires a special semiotic description. The circle is threaded on the tree trunk and continued by the figures of people that remind wheel spokes. As researches believe, this formation indicates the wheel of fortune. At the same time, this is a round table that serves up dishes to the gluttons by fortune. The absurdity of this table-wheel is in the fact that the circle is threaded on the tree trunk and the tree was able to grow only through a hole in the center. The strange construction in the center of the painting in the form of a table that is pierced by the tree continues two phantasmagorias of Bosch: the *Ship of fools* (figure 3), the *Tree-man* and the *Ship of fools in flames* (figures 4 and 5). The construction in the painting *Tree-man* is queer artificial-natural formation in the form of an egg-hollow.

In the *Ship of Fools* (figure 3), a mast is transformed into a tree. In both paintings, the center is a mast, a tree, some floating construction. Bruegel continues these Bosch's metaphors, relying upon their conceptuality, their basic meaning in the texts of the medieval European culture. In the context of the *Ship of fools* and *The land of Cockaigne*, the central sign formation of the painting in the form of a tree with a table-wheel acquires the character of developed concepts that are built one over another. The origin of the construction of the tree-ship itself in Bosch's paintings is connected with extensive verbal context. In the epoch of the Middle Ages, as far as Christianity is concerned, a ship was, as is widely known, a model of salvation (a Gothic cathedral as a ship that saves the souls of the sinners). A ship with a tree on it is a medieval modification of the Noah's Ark. The tree that grows on the ship marks salvation of life in the context of the story about the ark. In this context, Bosch's works gain a specific meaning. The gluttons of the *Tree-man* and the gluttons and libertines of the *Ship of fools* believe that they save their souls. Sign manifestation is produced in *The land of Cockaigne*: the construction of the mast of the "ship-ark" is still there, but there is no ship. P. Bruegel introduced a meaning into this sign manifestation: the land of idlers receives no salvation and one does not think of it here. The ship does not move and its mast turns into the center of gluttony (as it was interpreted previously in the *Ship of fools*). It should be noted that the *Allegory of gluttony and lust* and the *Ship of fools* by Bosch were two parts of one and the same tryptich (the tryptich did not survive as a whole). In other words, in *The land of Cockaigne*, Bruegel combined the sign systems of the two parts of one Bosch's work. In general, a developed conceptual scheme was formed.

The main features of the living construction by Bosch are spheric bodies, circles with dishes, the tree that grows through a spheric wooden body. These

features are retained and modified in Bruegel's *The land of Cockaigne*. The *Ship of fools* blames gluttons, dissolute monks. Their denouncement was conditioned by a conflict of the secular power and the church in the fifteenth century (Bosing 1973). But, according to the researcher, the *Ship of fools* was a larger generalization. Starting from Bosch's phantasmagorias, Bruegel made a symbolic formation that symbolizes the absurdity of *The land of Cockaigne*. Combination of the features of the construction of the *Tree-man* and the *Ship of fools* by Bosch generated something new — a synthetic, phantasmagoric, absurd sign formation: the tree-table of *The land of Cockaigne*. The conceptual scheme of Bruegel's innovation can be seen in the structures of the concepts and the meanings of the previous sign formations (Bosing 1973). The ship of idlers does not go anywhere, and the original concept of Noah's Ark means that there is no way of salvation. Bruegel made a larger and unconventional generalization: he blamed society. The tree that grows in the *Ship of fools*, instead of being a mast, is the semantic center of the ship, it indicates the upward aspiration of foolish thought. A fools' flag with a half-moon is fluttering there; the tree is piercing a delicious goose carcass, a fool with a knife in his hand is climbing up to get the goose. There is a wiseman's mask at the top of the tree. Somebody that is shouting a song points up at the tree by his hand.

Semantic and sign relations of the work rely upon developed relations of the representamens and visually active elements — signals. Similarly to other masterpieces of visual art, these relations in *The land of Cockaigne* are actualized in rather complicated organizing sign formations. The *organization of signals*, first of all, relies upon large color configurations that are close to a circle. Otherwise stated, the composition is based upon the interrelation of color circles and trapeziform configurations. *Similar configurations* are organizing means that at the same time intensify denotations of a symbolic character and form connotations. All major color configurations and active lines of the painting form a well-arranged formation. This effective organization of a layer of signals promotes actualization of various semantic "branches" of the work. Due to organizing features of s-shaped configurations, the meaning of idlers' lazy spreading is strengthened. Organizing circles and round configurations foster the intensification of sign systems of meal and gluttony. S-shaped organizing lines that link many visually active elements of the painting activate the signs of swinishness. On the whole, the rich color ornament of the painting emphasizes numerous signs of the prevailing metonymies, the leading meanings of the work.

Generally speaking, a common idea of Bruegel's work can be found in the interrelations of the basic concepts, metonymies, meanings of separate signs. Sleepy inertness, narrow-mindedness, stupidity, and gluttony of the elite of the society make the land unviable.

3. The way to falling

The *Parable of the blind* (Figure 13) illustrates Christ's words from the Gospel. The parable says: "Can the blind lead the blind? Shall they not both fall into the ditch?" These words are an allegory as Jesus spoke of scribes and Pharisees. Therefore the parable of the blind is interpreted as a parable of spiritual poverty, of the vices that make people blind, averting them from the beauty of life (Ionina 2000). The blind see no morals, they are in the dark (Stechow 1968; Roberts-Jones 2002). An image of a church also points at the moral-religious sense of the parable. As a result of combination of these verbal contexts, a conceptual scheme with a wide meaning is formed. Those who follow the leaders and ideas that lead away from morality will see a terrible end. The signs of symptoms of diseases on the eyes of the blind also correspond to the scheme. Ophthalmologists have diagnosed various eye diseases in the painting. There are also close concepts and schemes. The blind are depicted not as peasants or townspeople. They are similar to the Bosch's wayfarer (figures 14 and 15). They are going from a shed where there is a door-knocker — farther and farther from the human community. This group of people is a society that is living in the dark. This metonymy turns into a concept: darkness, spiritual poverty, following the leaders of spiritlessness lead humanity to fall. The conceptual scheme of the painting is based upon separate concepts. The central one is that of following one another and falling after the leader. The falling is shown as extensive in time; as the first falls, the second begins to fall, and the rest follow. The second must fall after the leader, the rest will fall after the second one. This course of falling is marked by specific sign means (turns of the angles, tilts, prevailing of vertical and horizontal tilts). The tilts form indexes of falling (figures 16 and 17). They are organized rhythmically, which produces dynamics. The alignment of the blind into a chain is emphasized by the relations of their figures — motions of their arms and legs, visual combinations of the parts of these figures. The structures of the work intensify the main denotative meaning — the falling of the blind. Researchers paid attention to exactly this — semantic — character of the rhythmical structure of *The blinds* (Arnheim 1974). Tilted angles of the figures and their rhythmical alternations form a fan-shaped structure. This rhythmical structure is the best way to express the inevitability of falling of all the blind. This is connected with the fact that the given structure is of regular character. All the axes of falling and walking figures have a single structure, changes in the tilt angles (figure 16). The structure is intensified by the rhythms of the elements: lines and configurations. In the sign system of the painting, a sign system of relations between the falling and those who are not yet aware of the falling is created. The faces of the people walking behind are full of humility. However, the last one is smiling with a satanic smile (Ionina 2000). In this row, the fourth figure in the middle

plays a peculiar role, which is developed in a specific sign system of the painting (figures 16 and 18). As researchers note, a specific effect is achieved due to this graduality of movement of the blind. The falling that happens slowly, step-by-step is illustrative. The spectator sees the catastrophe in parts. Due to the graduality of falling, he is supposed to feel his/her involvement in what is happening, to take part in the action, feel that he/she is the only one to stop the people walking behind.

The conceptual scheme of the painting is complemented with metonymies, metaphors, and connotations. The general meaning of it is intensified by the concept of the path of life. Bruegel places the action into rural scenery, typical for Flanders, and creates a realistic picture of this scenery. At the same time, both the figures of the blind, and the road with a pit, and the scenery are of a symbolic character. The symbols continue the sign systems of cultural origin. The sign system, similarly to *The land of Cockaigne*, continues the signs of Bosch's work. In Bosch's painting, *The wayfarer*, an allegory of the path of life was created. In another version of *The wayfarer*, the painting was connected with *The prodigal son (aka the wayfarer)*, written himself (Rotterdam, Museum Boymans van Beuningen). The sign means used by Bosch to indicate the path of life are built on the submission of the denotations to a sign system of a different level. *The wayfarer* is painted with the help of the metalanguage of the symbols and their abstract features rather than the language of icons and indexes. The concept to which both denotations and connotations submit prevails in it. The conceptuality of the work is stressed by conventional signs and their relations. In particular, the road along which the wayfarer is walking is conventionally separated from the grass by color. The flat character of the image contributes to the conventionality of color relations and, therefore, the conventionality of sign relations. Stressing the road line and its color contrast with the surrounding world indicates the path and its environment at the same time. Bruegel continued Bosch's basic concept with his visual sign elements (figure 15). The road that leads the blind to the pit is, at the same time, a sign system conventionally marked by color with their typical representaments. Similar to *The wayfarer*, the movement is conducted from top left to right downward. The blind are also hobbling on their thin, half-bent, weak feet shod in black boots. Like in *The wayfarer*, they are dressed in coats and are carrying thin sticks in their hands. Bosch's wayfarer is coming up to a cracked weak bridge that is dangerously hanging above the pit with water. Similarly, the writhed blind leaning on their sticks are coming up to the pit along a small road. Bruegel borrowed from Bosch the signs of the basic concept — a path of life — having combined it with its conceptual scheme. This concept allowed him to enrich the sense of the painting. In Bruegel's work, some typical visual sign systems of *The wayfarer* were also developed with their ominous meanings. In particular, angular and trapeziform configurations of the composition

of *The wayfarer* seem to be quoted in linear elongated configurations of the composition of *The blinds*. Bosch identified angular configurations of punky bones that are gnawed by ravens with the configurations of the part of the wayfarer's figure. The wayfarer's future is revealed in these repetitions: his bones on which the ravens will sit. It is no coincidence that he is cautiously looking around and driving away a roaring dog. The blind in the poses with angular outlines are holding each other with their sticks, and their close future is demonstrated ever more definitely than the wayfarer's destiny.

How elements of figures are accented by color and as they hold on to each other represents a special sign system. After all, Bruegel designated in structure of characters the models of society and the mental world of people (Somov 2009). Relations for a solution of this sign system have been specified earlier: 1) distinctions of figures (from central figure to the left) on light and dark tones; 2) accent on a figure in a white cape, and then on two falling; 3) the fourth figure from the left to the right is connected by color and brightness with the second and simultaneously with the sixth; 4) the stick which the fourth and the fifth hold is connected with a stick of the first and the second (it is parallel to it); 5) three light feet of the fifth and the sixth (three feet for two) are similar in color to the hand of the third and a foot of the second; 6) two feet, and also a white hat of the fifth focus upwards on a vertical to a dark tree. The tree leads the eye to the church on a hill. The importance of this hat is accented by a dark stain under a tree (Lapin 2008). Each blind figure, their relation to the church, their sequence in a sheaf designate a certain essence of the Fall of mankind. This sign system of a picture is a theme of independent research.

Thus, the concept and the sign peculiarities of the painting *The wayfarer* are developed within the conceptual model of *The blinds*. A developed conceptual scheme that relies upon the paradigmatics of visual sign systems is formed.

The connotations of the work develop its basic conceptual scheme and the accompanying meanings of falling and dynamics of the moving figures. The connotations of uncertainty accompany the metonymy of the blindness of the movement. Uncertainty of the blinds' motions that mark the instability and uncertainty of their moving in the world and loss of orientation is actualized in the configurations of human figures and particularly the silhouettes of the bending legs (figures 19). Similar to Bruegel's *The peasant dance* (Somov 2009), legs are important elements of the composition here and are arranged into an organizing structural formation. The drawing of the blinds' figures and clothes promote the connotative meaning of uncertainty of the moving blind. Bruegel deliberately and contrastingly separates the blinds' heads and coats from their thin legs. Dark feet that are lagging along the earth weakly and the blind that are holding each other with their hands and sticks form a connotative meaning. An impression is produced that people are holding on to each other following the leader but they are very weakly connected with the earth. They

are scarcely walking along it. A more general sense is formed: the people who believe in the leaders are weakly connected with the earth. This connotativeness and metonymic features of the work develop a general didactic meaning of the parable — warning the modern world against belief in authoritative leaders.

A particular role of the blinds' legs in the concept of the painting generates specific sign systems. They are organized into an independent connotative formation. Small configurations of the legs of the lagging blind in the connotation turn into large configurations of figures-ghosts that are strolling in the twilight. The rhythmical systems of the legs and those of the inverted legs plus ghosts are isomorphous and mirror-symmetrical (figure 19). This isomorphism considerably adds to the organization of the connotation. The legs look like exaggerated inverted s-shaped configurations that develop the general movement of falling. Heads and parts of the figures marked by dark color, coats, and capes form sharp trapeziform and triangular outlines that are symmetrical with the configurations of the legs. Heads are figures represent the same legs that are plodding upside down. This intensifies the meaning of falling, extending the signs of the plodding legs and falling figures on the entire surface of the image.

Similar to his other works, Bruegel used hidden connotations of living creatures in this painting. In particular, he repeated the outlines of a bird-headed monster from Bosch's *The garden of earthly delights* (1503–1504, Museo del Prado) in the outlines of the blind's figures (figures 20–24). This connotation supplements the meaning of the painting: the horrible end of the victims gobbled up by birds of prey or the martyrs of the Hell eaten by monsters (figures 25–28). To intensify this connotation, Bruegel created developed groups of configurations of bird-shaped contours within color composition.

The organization of signals is achieved through developed analogies of configurations, interrelations of lines, proportional relations of the sizes of similar elements. The basic organizing lines and configurations of the painting form connotative sign formations. The similarities of groups of elements acquire the character of developed system-structural formations. This is one of the most important peculiarities of Bruegel's artistic language. All of his organizing means turn into connotations that emotionally impact the spectators. And, vice versa, the connotations motivated by basic meanings are organized into various system-structural formations. *Developed organizing and connotative formations of the work* produce its many-sided emotional impact, extending the basic meanings of the parable. The existence of the imagined connotative world produces the effect of nonverbalized impact on a human. In a calm, lonely environment, its fullness of phantasmal creatures introduces a mystical character into the scenery and intensifies the phantasmagorical features of the painting.

On the whole, similar to the sign system of *The land of Cockaigne*, H. Bosch's concepts are synthesized with the author's concepts, forming a single

conceptual scheme of the work. This conceptual scheme is materialized in complicated sign systematicity of the metaphors, metonymies, denotations, connotations, organizing sign formations.

A close interrelation of allegories, metonymies, and concepts, their mutual transitions and transformations into each other are revealed in the course of analysis of P. Bruegel's works. This is attributed to the common semiotic nature of these three sign formations. An allegory is a manifestation of a metonymy in which the signifying side is concrete. Concepts can be viewed as sign formations in which metonymies develop and turn into systems of metonymies mutually related to each other and to the external signified. Historically, during the evolution of visual art, one can observe the transformation of metonymies from the state of allegories typical for the works of the late fifteenth century (the allegories of Lucas Cranach the Elder, Giovanni Bellini, Hieronymus Bosch, Hans Holbein the Younger, Hans Baldung Grien, and other masters of the fifteenth century) into Pieter Bruegel's metonymies (Somov 2009) and concepts that the author has strived to show in the current article.

Figure 1. *Pieter Bruegel the Elder, "The land of Cockaigne" (1567, oil on panel, 52 × 78 cm, Alte Pinakothek, Munich)*

Figure 2. Hieronymus Bosch, "Allegory of gluttony and lust" (1490–1500, oil on panel, 36 × 32 cm, Yale University Art Gallery, New Haven)

Figure 3. Hieronymus Bosch, "The ship of fools" (1490–1500, oil on wood, 58 × 33 cm, Musée du Louvre, Paris)

Figure 4. Hieronymus Bosch, "Tree-man" (c. 1470, pen and bistre, 277 × 211 mm, Graphische Sammlung Albertina, Vienna)

Figure 5. Hieronimus Bosch, "The ship of fools in flames" (pen and bistre, 176 × 153 mm, Akademie der bildenden Künste, Vienna)

Figure 6. "The land of Cockaigne." The signs of gluttony and their distribution in the composition of the painting. Pancakes on the roof correlate with "Netherlandish proverbs" (1559) by Bruegel. Given interrelations favor the sense of gluttony and intensify sign system of this meaning. Basic signs of dishes with food are structurally interconnected to idlers' signs — their figures and heads.

Figure 7. "The land of Cockaigne." The connotation of gluttony. The dishes with delicacies spread over the entire area of the painting. A huge dish in the bottom is similar to the whole hill of the land. It includes the figures of the idlers as delicacies.

Figure 8. "The land of Cockaigne." An organizing connotation of the painting. A large configuration embraces similar figures of idlers and intensifies the connotation in figure 6.

Figure 9. "The land of Cockaigne." The connotation of egg-shaped forms. Basic elements of the composition are organized by configurations that form the system of similar elements. These configurations intensify a sign of the egg on feet and connotations in figures 6 and 7.

Figure 10. *“The land of Cockaigne.”* Rotation of the wheel of fortune is rendered by a system of elongated configurations. These configurations are partly materialized, partly depicted in active straight lines of the contours. The dynamics of rotation and the meaning of the gyre of sleep are created.

Figure 11. *“The land of Cockaigne.”* Visually complex parts of the blinds' figures form contrasts — elements of the background. Configurations of the background are organized by general signs; they have complex contours with breaks of outlines, and angles with turns around the center. Visually similar parts of figures form main parts of the image. Configurations have mutual triangular and trapeziform contours. The given system of composition is characteristic of Bruegel (Somov 2009). The system of configurations such as this form parts that are segmented by smaller similar elements inside.

Figure 12. "The land of Cockaigne." The connotation of big swinishness.

Figure 13. Pieter Bruegel the Elder, "The parable of the blind leading the blind" (1568, tempera on canvas, 86 × 154 cm, Museo Nazionale di Capodimonte, Naples).

Figure 14. Hieronymus Bosch, "The wayfarer" (outer wings of the "Haywain" triptych, 1500–1502, oil on wood, 190 × 135 cm, Monasterio de San Lorenzo, El Escorial, Madrid).

Figure 15. *The influence of the signs of Bosch's "The wayfarer" on the composition of Bruegel's "The blinds."* This composition symbolizes the path of life, the temptations, and dangers of the path. The major among them are lust and gluttony (peasants), cruelty (the robbers that rob the wayfarer), malice, and slander (the roaring dog; Bosing 1973). The figure of the wayfarer and his movemenys became canonic signs of Bosch; he also showed this figure in the painting "Prodigal son (a.k.a. the Wayfarer)" (Rotterdam, Museum Boymans van Beuningen). The features of canonic drawing of the wayfarer's figure were developed in the figures of "The parable of the blind leading the blind" by Bruegel. The continuation of various signs promotes the relation of sign systems of "The blinds" with Bosch's concepts of the path of life. These are features of a canonical image of a path of life. As the wayfarer the blinds go from the west to the east [Robinson 1993: 118]. The analogy between the blinds and the wayfayer is enhanced by three signs: the slope of the figures, the inclined line of a pilgrim's staff, and the black hoods and boots.

Figure 16. "The blinds." The system of inclines of the moving figures of the blinds. Rhythm of the inclines designates transition to falling.

Figure 17. "The parable of the blind leading the blind." The system of signs of blinds' figures. Inclines are organized by points of focus.

Figure 18. *“The parable of the blind leading the blind.”* Basic figures of blinds and their location on a plane of the picture.

Figure 19. *“The parable of the blind leading the blind.”* Connotation of moving feet.

Figure 20. "The parable of the blind leading the blind." Connotation of travelling figures-shades. Acute-angled contours of feet silhouettes change into silhouettes of birds.

Figure 21. "The parable of the blind leading the blind." Connotation of bird-shaped monsters.

Figure 22. "The parable of the blind leading the blind." Connotation-phantasmagoria of a big bird.

Figure 23. "The parable of the blind leading the blind." Connotation of birdlike monsters. Beaks gulp down their victims, which continues Bosch's vision.

Figure 24. "The parable of the blind leading the blind" (fragment). Connotation birds and the clothes of the blinds. The drawing of folds promotes visions. The drawing of the blinds' clothes is twisted in a complicated manner and the complicity of their color mosaics continues the connotations of bird-shaped monsters. The connotations of devilish forces created in Bosch's paintings followed the idea of materialization of the offspring of the fallen angels in monsters (Bosing 1973), of the fullness of the surrounding world by devilish forces. The search of devils in sixteenth and seventeenth centuries met these ideas. Filling the paintings with devilish connotations was started by Bosch and was continued and developed in Bruegel's works. Unlike Bosch, Bruegel to a greater extent concealed devils and monsters in the connotations of the paintings. In the painting "The blinds," this approach was used to mark and express the spiritlessness of the lagging crowd of the blinds and the presence of the devilish forces.

Figure 25. "The parable of the blind leading the blind." Connotation of bird-shaped monsters. The drawing and color areas of blinds' clothes form signs of birds' heads.

Figure 26. "The parable of the blind leading the blind." Connotation of monsters' appearances indicates the devil's presence.

Figure 27. "The parable of the blind leading the blind." Connotation of the monsters' appearances or the devil's presence.

Figure 28. “The parable of the blind leading the blind.” Connotation of the monsters’ appearances or the devil’s presence. Connotations on figures 27 and 28 strengthen each other:

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